

Development, Inclusiveness – Sustainability of Pastoralism & its Reality (A Study on Somali Pastoralists, Ethiopia (East Africa))

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Abstract

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The word “development” means making better life for everyone (Peet and Hartwick, 2010). This is possible when people in nations are free to access resources equally with dignity. Today this meaning swirl bitter arguments and fierce debates from academics and development thinkers because of uneven and impromptu way of development are seen mostly in developing countries (Asia, African, and Latin America). As a result, many people are missing their opportunities to access resources; equity and justice become a debatable issue. Therefore, people are becoming economically marginalized thereby socially excluded. Hence poverty, hungers, displacements, economic refugees, conflictions etc. are seen growing. Therefore, this development has been criticised by many development think tanks (Santos, 1970, Wallerstein, 1979, Sen, 1991, etc.) but no paradigm change has been noticed. It remains within spectrum of academia only. Today when most of the developing nations have massive economy , populating fordism to enhance national account like Gross domestic product and Gross national income (Peet and Hartwick,2010) still human’s conditions remain unchanged that indicate the fruits of the development are reaching to a few. Therefore, this study is an attempt to redefine development which is inclusive- sustainable for indigenous people like pastoralists in Jigjiga, Ethiopia

Key Words: Development, Inclusiveness, Pastoralism, Sustainability, Resources

Prelude

The word “development” means making better life for everyone (Peet and Hartwick, 2010). This is possible when people in nations are free to access resources equally with dignity. Today this meaning swirl bitter arguments and fierce debates from academics and development thinkers because of uneven and impromptu way of development are seen mostly in developing countries (Asia, African, and Latin America). As a result, many people are missing their opportunities to access resources; equity and justice become a debatable issue. Therefore, people are becoming economically marginalized thereby socially excluded. Hence poverty, hungers, displacements, economic refugees, conflictions etc. are seen growing elsewhere. Therefore, this development has been criticised by many development think tanks (Santos, 1970, Wallerstein, 1979, Sen, 1991, etc.) but no paradigm change has been noticed. It remains within spectrum of academia only. Today when most of the developing nations have massive economy , populating fordism to enhance national account like Gross domestic product and Gross national income (Peet and Hartwick,2010) still human’s conditions remain unchanged that indicate the fruits of the development are reaching to a few.

Therefore, since last few decades world see much social unrest in some parts of Asia and Latin America and most parts in Africa, has become a common phenomenon here .Uneven development-frequent policy motions fueled more into social unrest are seen mostly in African nations where the Ethiopia may not be exceptional. As a result many development activities are jeopardized. Subsequent rising internal displacements, conflictions have put more pressure on resources. Unnecessary people’s movement, using transports for resource mobilization on crisis, create nothing but huge pollution, the greenhouse gases means global warming (Climate Action, 2021) that lead to changing environment and climatic behaviour (Bhattacharjee et al., 2021) which ultimately distress nature, natural resources thereby many ways in life and livelihoods to common man in general, pastoralists in particular whose life line depend on nature. According to International Monetary Fund Reports,2021 (Ivanyna et al.,2021) the frequency and magnitude of natural disasters which had a great impact on the GDP of advanced and low economy countries (see Figure 1 below) at the cost of huge human deaths there.

Figure 1
Natural Disasters and its frequency and magnitudes year 1980-2020

Source: (Ivanyna, et al., 2021)

Note. Figure.1. “Climate action to unlock the inclusive growth story of the 21st century” International Monetary Fund (WP/21/147). Ivanyna, M., Stern, N., Oman, W., & Bhattacharya, A. (2021). Climate Action to Unlock the Inclusive Growth Story of the 21st Century. Copy right . “Permission not sought”

The Jigjiga in Somali Region has about 2.51% of (9270,05 population) are pastoralists (CSA, 2007). Over the past few decades this pastoral area was marked by various vulnerability like drought - chronic shortage of food grains, degradation of land and grazing sites . This indigenous people live ecclesiastical life, they get food and forage in nature as seen through their land using behaviour (see Table 1). Climatic whimsies fueled with social unrests ultimately are pushing them into the brink of economic marginalization - social exclusions.

Table 1
Land using behaviour of Pastoralists

Land using pattern	Frequency	Percentage
Common land	117	75.5
Individual land	17	11.0
Community land	21	13.5
Total	155	100.0

Though United Nations' are working closely, still more needs to be done for inclusiveness, environmentally sustainable development activities. Recent past inclusive green economy also found a pathway to sustainable development, is on discourse. This economic model gives priority to environment, social externalities for peace and prosperity of humanbeings. So we should not miss this opportunity. .Development is needed but at what cost? It should be nature friendly; inclusive that should protect, preserve and promote natural resources where pastoralists can play major role in the way to find out their sustainable livelihood options. Within this understanding the following objectives are developed.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the challenges of pastoralism in the present context of development concepts in Jigjiga
- To examine as to how this concept posed as life and livelihood challenge for pastoralist community
- To find Institutional roles for lasting solutions to the challenge

Review of Literature

A few decades and so after World War II around 1950s development studies were insulated within the preview of traditional/ classical-neo classical economical thoughts in nature. These thoughts have basically emphasized about how to study society and their economic practices quantitatively (Harriss, 2005) with ultimate goal to see how the developed nations contribute in the development of poor nations. Like- wise “development policy came to be strongly associated with classical economic theory during this period”(Robert B. Potter,2014). Therefore, within classical think tanks like (Marx, 1976) looked the development as accumulation of wealth and capital that accumulate based on socio-economic standings of people which invented a new

avenue of class relations, exploitation and competition among working classes in the socio-economic history in the world.

The year of 1960's was an emergence of radicalism politics in societies that developed 'dependency theory', where (Dos Santos, 1970) defined in such a way that made a narrow line between dominated and dependent countries for sustaining economic growth and development. Political economic or structuralism approaches of human geography also took a space of development studies as it is seen from David Harvey's land mark publication in 1973. In mid 80's and thereafter the neo-conservatism and neo-liberalisms concept slowly became an important course of discussion in various academics and non-academics platforms where free trades, unregulated free markets were the central position of discussion for development of nations. Then in 90's Modernisation and post modernisation concepts took over as a central positions of development which were on discourse even today where (Sachs,2005) presented his views as "economic development is a ladder with the rungs representing steps up the path to economic well-being". (Sen, 1983, 1999) also argues that "economic growth should not be viewed as an end in itself, but as the means to the achievement of a much wider set of objectives by which economic and social development should be measured". (Alkire, 2002 and Nussbaum, 2003) also highlighted to "establish a list of human capability priorities or even to systematically defend a set of basic functioning, or capabilities, in line with basic needs". It is true that majority people in the third world society are unable to meet their basic needs, although development activities are going on but that fruits are reaching to the few. Therefore, majority people are pauperized. "Rising rates of Illiteracy, more areas are affected by "famine, and so on, become the identifiers of a 'Third World society', that is, one in need of intervention to foster cultural change and the economic growth necessary to resolve these social ills" (Escobar, 1994; Kothari, 2006b). Even it was not been sacrificed deliberately, many suffers because of increased percentage of people in social exclusion and economic marginalization that harmed future generations and their relationship with environment that mutilate to the nature. As a result of that frequent changes of climate are seen globally (UNDP, 2007) whose lion shares of responsibilities may go to developed nations and impact of climate changes permeate to developing countries also that is found by (Crutzen, 2002) in his study "It is true that any economic activity globally or in nations over the past few decades has made much challenge for

relationship between ecosystems and environment that has attracted many academics and global think tanks . In this context (Desanker, *et. al*; 2001) also gone one step forward to conclude his findings where he viewed about the severity of climate change that can be seen in untimely rain, sometime no rain, droughts and many other hazardous forms in nature which has significant impact on African communities and their economies also. Africa in general and the Ethiopia in particular where the rural settlements are indigenous people based, marked with their ethnic identity. These peoples' livelihood mostly depends upon livestock use pasture and forages with meager practicing of subsistence agriculture moving away from modernity and modern practices thus marked as pastoralists here. (Srinivasan, *et. al.*, 2008).rightly viewed that this indigenous people are nature lovers, live ecclesiastical life , sometime they are victimised as impacts on ecosystem thereby their greater reliance on natural resource based livelihoods are exposed to threats.

Thus development –climatic whimsies mostly have great impact on crops and livestock of this people” (Bhattacharjee et al., 2021). As a solution mechanism to these problems, institutional roles have to be recognised for structural change and development (Bhattacharjee et al.,2021) that “structural factors need to be addressed at regional, national and potentially international levels and are critical in determining whether local livelihood and coping strategies become meager ‘strategies for survival’ or ‘strategies for success” (Brooks,2006) besides, climate action may play important role to show more opportunistic ways for inclusiveness, resilient and sustainable growth (Bhattacharya et al., 2021) . Today another economy model is on discourse i.e. green growth model. This economic model gives priority to environment, social externalities for peace and prosperity of humanbeings thereby sustainability.

To bring a lasting solutions to all these challenges, development is imperative but at what cost?. It should not be at the cost of environment, ecology any more. Therefore, the discourse of green economy appeared as main discussion issues at the Rio de Janeiro + 20 Conference(UN, 2012), which called simultaneously for a ‘green economy’ and ‘sustained economic growth’. Green growth has since become a dominant response to increasingly serious warnings about climate change and ecological breakdown (Dale, et. al., 2016).

Figure 2
Conceptual Framework

Study Area

Jiggiga Woreda in Somali Region was selected purposively out of total 12 Woredas since the problem exist here.

Study Area

Map. 1. Source. (CSA, 2007)

Demography

Based on the (2007) Census conducted by the Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia (CSA), the total population in the Region of Somali have around (7,455,220)(CSA,2007) comprising of 3,472,490 men and 3,972,729(CSA, 2007) (see Bhattacharjee et al., 2021), are women. 80% were pastoralists and farmers (CSA, 2007) (also see Bhattacharjee et al., 2021), The estimated population was 11,748,998 in 2017 (CSA, 2007) (also see Bhattacharjee et al., 2021)

Climatic Condition

“The region is characterised as semi-arid with the average rainfall of 500 mm per annum. The region has a potential annual evaporation rate of 3,100 mm and as a result, the area is deficient in moisture in all the months of the year. Most of the area is rangeland laying in the arid zone and semi-arid zone and is highly susceptible to drought”.(Assessment Mission Reports, Drought and Floods Stress Livelihoods and Food security,1999)

Livestock

“In 2005 farmers in the Somali Region had 459,720 cattle (representing 10.19%% of Ethiopia's total cattle), 1,463,000 sheep (20.66%), 1,650,970 goats (50.02%), 1,291,550 donkey (30.66%), 5,3165, 260 camels (96.2%), 154,670 poultry of all species (0.5%), and 5,330 beehives (0.12%)”(CSA, 2007)(also see Bhattacharjee et al., 2021),

Research Design

Descriptive research design was found suitable for this study where quantitative and qualitative data were collected after determining a suitable sample size from the Universe(9270.05)

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Non probability and probability (both) the sampling methods were followed for this research in which purposively Jigjiga Woreda had been selected. This Woreda consists of 10 kebeles (as called villages), out of only two kebeles (Kebele 06 &10) were randomly selected since the population is homogenous in nature. Using suitable formula sample size (155) had been determined in considering (92% confidence level, 0.08 % level of precision)

Data Sources and Collection Method

Mixed methods approach adopted in collecting data through primary sources like front to front interviewed with respondents besides focus grouped discussion and discussion with key informants. Besides secondary data collected through secondary sources like published books, research articles, theses and also from government records. After collecting data using suitable statistical tools and technique data was analysed. Based upon conclusion, certain suggestions are given for formulating effective policies.

Results and Discussion

In 21st century also most of the rural areas globally are found to be suffering from extreme poverty and famines besides social exclusion and environmental disadvantaged, are also seen in African continents where the Ethiopia may not be exceptional to that. Here local climatic conditions also have pivotal role to protect and promote natural resources alongwith socio-economic and political factors that play major role not only for rural agricultural activities but also building pathways for economic development as a whole(Florin and Corneliu, 2020). Subsistence agricultural practices with rejuvenated livestock production systems are still traditional in nature which have widespread across rural areas here in this vulnerability of natural hazards particularly recurrent droughts (see FAO,2000 reports) where it shows “up to 8.7

million were affected by the drought that beset Ethiopia in 1994)". "This drought resulted in the death of about 1 million people and 1.5 million livestock" (FAO, 2000). This has a great effect on natural resources.

Therefore, agricultural productivity remains poor which led to famine and massive migration to other countries also. To address this situation, today many development activities in the line of sustainable development goals (SDGs) are on progress. But reaching the appropriate targets and goals within SDGs framework become quite challenging task here due to negligence and poor political wills in using proper remedying mechanisms. Therefore, most parts of the nation, the impromptu ways of development activities are visible. These development practices have not only invited better debates across academics society in policy making process but also produced many inequalities within and among society; hence injustice to access resources is seen rampant and pervasive here.

Therefore to ameliorate this situation, institutions have no other options other than to make frequent policy shifts that create much confusions in bottom level functionaries to deliver the effective governance in regional and local level where mostly pastoralists are living that lead social unrests, conflicts (see Figure 3 below), consequence is that unnecessary mobilization of resources, human movements, internal displacements, raising more economic refugees in other place within this nation or near-by countries which made to think in redefining of development perspectives and strategies today.

Figure 3
Actors of land conflict between farmers and pastoralist in the study

Therefore, redefining development process should consider local infrastructure and challenges in order to invent historical link with their life and livelihoods pattern to bring any change (Escobar, 1995, 98) beside expanding the freedoms, liberties to be valued in their own rights (Sen, 1999) then only each individual can lead a life that have reason to value. It is possible through recognition of indigenous knowledge, effective participation vulnerable people like pastoralists for giving better meaning of development equity and justice may restore to them but “understanding the two-way relationship between development and inequality is the real challenge for producing a development strategy focused on fostering pro-poor or inclusive growth” (Bhattacharjee et al., 2021). This may be easy through developing political wills and abled leaderships of a nation. Poverty (see Figure 4), malnourishments along with burgeoning population in most of the rural areas still are found to be critical issues need urgent attention at rural Africa which may be a cause of concern for poor in accessing to critical amenities and basic services like health, education, hygienic drinking water, sanitation etc. As a result child mortality rate is still high (see Figure 5) though appreciable level of improvement is seen.

Figure 4
Absolute Number in Poverty

Figure 5
Child Mortality Rate(Per 1000 live birth)

Source: Howard White,H (2014)

This condition of human life may further inflate climate change- depletion of natural resources, dilapidation of land, besides change of human nature, behaviour and culture - political instability, corruption, conflicts etc. It draws real scenario of rural areas mostly in developing countries where Ethiopia is also not outstanding. The rapid growth of apparent investments from emergent economies is also inviting a new threat to the ecology and environment particularly for most of the developing nations that is making serious coercions not only to health but also living of many people.

In an era of record commodity prices and corporate profits, the gap is growing between transnational industrialists and the rural communities who live on a treasure of natural assets but

are often excluded from benefit sharing while suffering ecological impacts” (Khoday and Perch, 2012a)(82% of total animal in Africa use rangeland comparing other countries in the world(Gahey,MC, et al., 2014) . Higher expectations have now emerged within global civil society for more effective, accountable and participatory use of the environment as a public good, and to prevent the impact of pollution on poor and vulnerable people. In this context, “rural resilience and circular economy are key strategic directions to further develop rural economies and reduce socioeconomic inequalities and environmental injustice coupled with access to proper education”(Florin,Mihai,& Corneliu,Iatu.2020). A linear economy based on “take-make-dispose” model feed by consumerism society is harmful for the environment and long-term sustainability of urban and rural areas”(ibid,2020)

Alternative views’ on development were supported in many ways that include such development which is participatory in nature. At the same time, it needs to give more priority to indigenous knowledge particularly on environmental issues. This postmodernisation epoch always put stress in denial of modernism may not be acceptable now while considering realities of the development particularly for developing and under developing nations in the world. Early standpoints of development process particularly in least developed nations like Top Down and Bottom Up approach has not shown any lasting solutions of particular challenge that the people are facing now; instead it includes new ideas for another development. Likewise many approaches were in action previously to achieve sustainable development goals and sustainability but these all approaches ultimately flouted the value of indigenous people and their knowledge (Briggs, John, 2014) to make effective uses of local resources. In a long run these enigmatic intentions may invite the fruits of all growths and developments purely on market based where only a few can reach there.

Conclusion:

We all have to accept that this century is meant for century for change. It changes in behaviour of socio-economic and political life of people with utmost utility of natural resources. This attitudes are affecting in maintaining better relationship between ecology and environment whose victims are humankind. Therefore, this change will be meaningful when humankind have better life and livelihoods options. It should bring global society together through such meaningful way that may preserve, protect and promote each other resources without putting many taxes to the ecology and environment in nations and in globe. Today when we discuss

about development and sustainable development issues particularly for emerging economies countries like Africa, the sustainable development issues always remain in peripheral to the central of development discourse in which lion shares of the responsibility may go to developed nations. Many developed country's persistent behaviour in continuing growth of their economy need to focus on sustainable development with inclusiveness.

Today nature of change in global economies is such that it influences the consumer behaviour such large extent that producers are also confused to produce their products which is creating another room for resource wastage. To mitigate this issue, a recent past the concept of green economy has achieved in such certain height that become an important tool in developing economy without much disturbance of natural resources in any nation globally. Again this concept of green economy is able to strengthen the social networking systems through which many marginalized community may be able to access the resources without having much hurdles and unnecessary movements. Therefore, it reduces much pressure on natural resources in particular which are already at scrunch. Like way, many mechanisms are being developed in the form of innovations to ensure optimal utilization of resources but it remains in the hand of political leaders and their political wills.

Therefore, development, inclusiveness-sustainability may be made in reality through strong political wills besides it needs involvement of youth centric approaches in realising basic necessity of rural people in general and pastoralists in particular. It should cover public utility services, use effectively technological apparatus giving due respects to socio-economic-political and environmental aspects in such a manner that can make better rural-urban linkage. In addition to this, it needs to build up certain creativity which may show the way to find funding mechanisms to build climate smart economies for African countries in general and Ethiopia in particular so that indigenous people like pastoralists may find a new avenue in finding their sustainable livelihood options naturally in order to make their peaceful settlements.

Suggestions:

- Need innovative policies and programs interventions.
- Motivate more regional and local level pupil's participation.
- Create need based development projects/programs.
- Need to reduce more spill-over effects
- Develop common global platforms for indigenous people like pastoralists to promote their experience, knowledge and practices.
- Need to develop certain mechanism at nodal level so that indigenous pupil's voice can be heard and their issues can be addressed at appropriate time that ultimately may reduce unnecessary mobility of this people, peace and prosperity can be gained.
- Need strengthen of monitoring and evaluation systems in each level of government functionaries in order to make accountability and transparency in optimal utilization of natural resources in order to achieve sustainable goals and inclusive development.

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